

IMPACT OF FINANCIAL DEVELOPMENT ON SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: THE MODERATING EFFECT OF FINANCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the moderating effect of financial infrastructure on the relationship between financial development and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria from 1986 to 2023, employing the Vector Error Correction Model to analyze the data that were sourced from the World Development Indicators and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The findings revealed that financial development, the interaction between financial development and financial infrastructure, financial deepening and financial infrastructure and institutional quality had positive and significant impact on sustainable economic growth. Meanwhile, the interaction of financial infrastructure with FinTech showed positive but insignificant impact. On the contrary, financial infrastructure and the moderating effect of financial infrastructure with financial inclusion revealed insignificant negative impact on sustainable economic growth. The findings further indicated that deviations from the long-run equilibrium were corrected at a rate of 0.11% per annum. Based on these findings, the study recommends strengthening Nigeria's financial infrastructure through improved digital systems, regulatory reforms, and reliable payment networks to enhance the transmission of financial development to sustainable growth.

Keywords: Financial development, Infrastructure, Deepening, Nigeria

JEL Codes: G20, G21, O16, E44, O40

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainable economic growth remains an important objective for Nigeria; however, the economy continues to experience challenges in terms of limited financial inclusion, intermediation, and levels of institutional quality and infrastructural base. Efficient financial development, which enhances resource mobilization and allocation, has come to be seen as playing an essential role in growth, especially in financial systems conducive to productive investment as well as innovation (World Bank, 2021; Schumpeter, 1911; World Economic Forum, 2023; Central Bank of Nigeria, CBN, 2022). Literature on financial development indicated its potential to be an important driver of economic growth; however, this potential may not be effective without the presence of complementary factors, such as levels of infrastructures and technology adoption (Salami & Oluseyi, 2013; Mogbo, 2025; Alabi et al., 2024).

Financial infrastructure such as bank branches, payment systems, as well as digital systems, can help boost the efficacy of financial development by increasing accessibility, minimizing transactional costs, and enabling credit allocation (Saramu et al., 2024; Noor et al., 2020; Echu et al., 2024). However, financial infrastructure development has not been in the same pace across Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria (2023) reported that even though there were 5,810 financial access points in Nigeria in the year 2023, they were mostly concentrated in urban areas, which caused rural areas to remain unbanked and poorly connected to the formal financial system. This unequal distribution restricts the access of the population to financial services, promotes the regional disparities in access to loans and deposits, and reduces the financial sector's ability to foster inclusive and sustainable economic growth. Financial inclusion and deepening ensure that larger portions of the population are actively involved in economic activities, thus enhancing economic development in terms of sustainability as well as equity (Ukoh & Ibe, 2024; Uruakpa et al., 2019; Tidjani & Madouri, 2024). However, inefficiencies in infrastructure or institutional systems may hinder any potential that can be gained from these financial tools or systems (Samuel et al., 2024; Adebayo, 2025).

With reference to Nigeria, research findings have indicated that the relationship between financial development and infrastructure is a critical determinant for boosting financial outcomes, while the adoption of fintech can further enhance the value of the financial system (Madu et al., 2024; Inuwa et al., 2022). Nevertheless, the sustainability of economic growth is acknowledged to be precarious due to low levels of support and integration of digital financial systems (Kalu et al., 2019; Noor et al., 2020). Based on the above-mentioned factors, this study aims to explore the moderating role of financial infrastructure on the relationship between financial development and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria, using data from 1986 to 2023.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Review

Schumpeterian Theory of Financial Intermediation

Schumpeter (1911) argues that entrepreneurs and the credit-creation role of financial intermediaries are central to economic development, as banks mobilize and allocate resources toward innovative and productive ventures. The theory assumes discontinuous innovation, effective financial intermediation, and that credit allocation is more critical for growth than the sheer volume of savings. Its key strength lies in providing a clear micro-foundation linking financial development to innovation-driven and sustained economic growth (King & Levine, 1993; Levine, 1997). Empirical evidence reinforces this, showing that deeper and more efficient financial systems support technological progress, productivity gains, and long-run growth (Beck, Levine & Loayza, 2000; Aghion, Howitt & Mayer-Foulkes, 2005). However, the theory has been criticized for its descriptive nature and lack of a formal mechanism to address information asymmetries, as well as its limited treatment of financial inclusiveness and technological change in modern finance (Levine, 2005; Demirgüç-Kunt & Klapper, 2013; Sahay et al., 2020). Its relevance to this study is strong: financial inclusion widens access to credit for innovative activities; financial deepening expands the capacity of intermediaries to fund long-term, growth-enhancing investments; and financial technology lowers transaction and information costs, strengthening the finance–innovation–sustainable growth nexus and making growth more inclusive and resilient.

2.2. Review of Empirical Literature

Abdulmumini et al. (2025) explored the relationship between financial inclusion, corruption, political instability, and economic growth in Nigeria. The study used the Autoregressive Distributed Lag model (ARDL). The results showed that financial inclusion and literacy level have a positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria, while political instability has a negative impact on economic growth. Mogbo (2025) used ARDL and cointegration analysis to evaluate the long-run relationship between financial development and economic performance in Nigeria (1994-2023). The findings revealed that financial development had a favourable impact on growth, but the effect was statistically significant only when financial infrastructure measures were included, implying that banking access moderates the finance-growth relationship. Adebayo (2025) used the ARDL model to assess the impact of financial development on Nigerian economic growth from 1981 to 2023. The study included control factors such as government spending, investment, trade openness, oil prices, and labour force to provide a thorough economic assessment. The empirical results showed that the financial development index had no statistically significant effects on economic growth in both the short and long run.

The relationship between financial sector development and economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2022 was examined by Zakari and Mohammed (2024). The study employed the ARDL and the Toda-Yamamoto Granger Non-Causality Test in the analysis of the relationship. The results showed that financial deepening, stock market capitalization, and the real interest rate had a positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The causality results showed no causal relationship was found between GDP and financial deepening. Madu et al. (2024) examined the impact of financial development on Nigeria's economic growth from 1981 to 2021. The data were evaluated using the ARDL limits cointegration approach, and the long-run results revealed that financial development contributed positively to Nigeria's economic growth, but inflation and unemployment had a negative impact. In the short term, Nigeria's broad money supply had a negative impact on economic growth.

In 20 SSA nations, Alabi et al. (2024) conducted an empirical investigation of the role of infrastructure in the relationship between financial development and economic growth. Using data from 1985 to 2018 and the pooled mean group (PMG) estimation technique, the empirical results indicated a non-linear relationship between financial development and economic growth, with the positive impact outweighing the negative one over the long and short terms. However, the non-linear estimate showed that financial development had a mixed influence on economic growth, showing that it had a beneficial effect up to a certain point before hurting growth. Saramu et al. (2024) similarly conducted research to examine the impact of financial inclusion on economic growth in Nigeria, utilizing the ordinary least squares (OLS) method. Findings revealed a positive and statistically significant relationship between credit to the private sector and economic growth, while ATM transactions showed a positive but statistically insignificant relationship with economic growth.

Echu et al. (2024) investigated the role of digital finance in promoting sustainable development in the Nigerian economy. To achieve the study's goals, a positivist approach was taken with a sample of 384 respondents. The data was analyzed through regression analysis and the results found considerable effect on sustaining the development of Nigeria. Joseph et al. (2024) explored the link between financial development and inclusive growth in 27 African nations using panel data for 18 years. The study utilized the Mean Group (MG) Estimator to address the heterogeneity issue. The results showed financial development indicators have a significant impact on inclusive

growth in the long term, though the strength and direction of the relationships differ across financial indicators, with ATMs having a lower effect.

Tidjani and Madouri (2024) analyzed the relationship between financial technology, financial inclusion and sustainable development, focusing on the African region. The study analyzed data from 25 African countries between 2011 and 2019, employing econometric techniques such as dynamic panel methods (two-step SGMM) and static panel approaches. The findings revealed that financial inclusion and FinTech significantly and positively influenced sustainable development. However, an interesting observation was that the interaction between financial inclusion and FinTech showed a weak but significant negative effect. Samuel et al. (2024) examined the impact of FinTech on economic growth and financial inclusion in Nigeria using quarterly data from 1999 to 2020. The study employed the Johansen cointegration test, the Granger non-causality test, and the Toda–Yamamoto procedure. The findings indicated that FinTech contributed to economic growth and financial inclusion by reducing income inequality and poverty rates. Additionally, the results revealed the presence of unidirectional, bidirectional, and feedback causality between the variables. Using OLS regression techniques, Ukoh and Ibe (2024) investigated how financial deepening affected Nigeria's economic growth between 1999 and 2022. The study indicated that there was a significant and positive relationship among money supply, private sectors' lending and economic development in Nigeria.

Another study by Inuwa et al. (2022) investigated the impact of fintech on Nigeria's growth and development in the wake of the COVID-19 recovery. To that end, 415 bank customers were surveyed, and the data was analysed using the Point Likert-Scale structural equation model (PLS-SEM). The results indicated that sustainability and transaction efficiency have a positive and significant impact on Nigeria's growth and development. Sennuga et al. (2021) analyzed the effect of financial development on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data over the period 1980 and 2019. The method of analysis was OLS, and the results indicated that real interest rate, gross domestic saving were inversely related to economic growth when combined while domestic credit to the private sector was positively related. Noor et al. (2020) investigated the relationships between financial inclusion, financial literacy, and financial technology (FinTech) in Indonesia's economy. The research, based on an analysis of thirty journals and reports, found that demographic factors such as gender, age, education, and occupation influenced the advancement of financial inclusion, literacy, and technology adoption. Expanding on FinTech's broader impact, the study examined China's provincial data from 2011 to 2018, demonstrating that FinTech innovation and green finance significantly promoted green economic growth, though the effects were uneven across regions. Eastern China experienced far greater benefits compared to central and western areas.

Using the ARDL model, Ademokoya (2020) investigated the relationship between the financial sector and sustainable development in Nigeria from 1986 to 2015. According to the study's findings, Nigeria's sustainable development was greatly and favourably impacted by the banking and stock markets. Kalu et al. (2019) investigated the finance-growth nexus in Nigeria from 1981 to 2017, using the ARDL and Nonlinear ARDL (NARDL) models. Financial deepening indicators were found to positively and significantly affect the growth of the Nigerian economy, while financial access was found to insignificantly affect economic growth linearly and nonlinearly. Kamalu et al. (2019) looked into the causal relationship between financial developments, financial inclusion, trade openness, foreign direct investment, and economic growth in Nigeria between

1970 and 2018. The non-Granger causality Toda and Yamamoto test, the Gregory and Hansen cointegration test, the Ng Perron, and the Zivot Andrew unit roots test were also employed in this investigation. The results showed a one-way relationship between financial inclusion and growth and a two-way causal association between financial development and economic growth. Trade openness and economic growth do not, however, cause one another to grow.

Uruakpa et al. (2019) investigated the impact of financial inclusion on economic growth of Nigeria for the period 2003 – 2015. The study made use of the ordinary least square technique (OLS) of multiple regression analysis. The empirical results show that deposits of rural branches of commercial banks and ATM transactions exerted a positive and significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria while loans of rural branches of commercial banks revealed a negative and insignificant impact. Salami and Oluseyi (2013) examined the impact of financial sector development on the Nigerian economic growth in view that an efficient financial system is essential for building a sustained economic growth and an open vibrant economic system. The OLS method of the regression analysis was employed, and it was found that financial development, proxied by ratio of liquidity liabilities to GDP, real interest rate, ratio of credit to private sector to GDP positively impacted on economic growth in Nigeria. The study also revealed that only the real interest rate was negatively related.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Theoretical Framework

The study is anchored on the Schumpeterian Theory of Financial Intermediation, which emphasized the importance of financial intermediaries in the process of economic development. According to this theory, financial intermediaries have a crucial role to play, especially in the mobilization of savings and in the efficient allocation of credit for innovative and productive investments. This theory is the most suitable for this study since it could explain how financial development could lead to economic growth, especially in the creation of credit, allocation of resources, and financing of innovation. It provides a good foundation for understanding how financial development can spur economic growth through better access to finance.

3.2. Model Specification

This study adapts and modifies the model of Salami and Oluseyi (2013). The model was adapted because some of the variables of this study were included in their model and they are good in explaining the relationship between financial development and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. The model of Salami and Oluseyi (2013) adapted for this study is thus specified functionally as;

$$RGDP = f (M2GDP, RINTR, CRGDP) \quad 3.1$$

Where, GDP = Real Gross Domestic Product; M2GDP = Percentage on money supply to GDP; CRGDP = Credit to private sector as a share of GDP. This current study therefore modifies the model and it is stated as;

$$ADNS = f (FDEVT, FIN, FDEVT * FIN, FI * FIN, FD * FIN, FINTEC * FIN, INSQ) \quad 3.2$$

Where, ADNS = Adjusted net savings, proxy for sustainable economic growth; FDEVT = Financial development; FIN = Financial infrastructure, proxy by number of bank branches; FDEVT*FIN = Interaction between financial development and financial infrastructure; FI*FIN = Interaction between financial inclusion and financial infrastructure; FD*FIN = Interaction between financial deepening and financial infrastructure; FINTEC*FIN = Interaction between financial technology and financial infrastructure; INSQ = Institutional quality. The model can be expressed econometrically as in equation 3.3.

$$ADNS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 FDEVT_{t-1} + \beta_2 FIN_{t-1} + \beta_3 FDEVT * FIN_{t-1} + \beta_4 FI * FIN_{t-1} + \beta_6 FD * FIN_{t-1} + \beta_7 FINTEC * FIN_{t-1} + \beta_8 INSQ_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad 3.3$$

Where, t-1 is the lagged value of the variables; ln = Natural logarithm; μ_t is the stochastic error terms which explain other variables that cannot be captured in the model; β_0, β_1 to β_8 are the slopes of the coefficients.

3.2. Estimation Techniques and Procedure

This section outlines the estimation technique that is used in measuring the variables and the procedures that are employed in implementing them. To estimate the parameters, the study relied on the Vector Error Correction Model, which is appropriate because it captures both the short-run dynamics and long-run equilibrium adjustments among variables that are cointegrated in a multivariate time-series framework. The time series data used in the study was tested for stationarity using the Augmented Dickey–Fuller Test, which is widely applied to determine the order of integration of variables and to avoid spurious regression results. Furthermore, the Johansen Cointegration Test was employed to establish whether a stable long-run equilibrium relationship exists among the variables before estimating the VECM.

3.3. Nature and Sources of Data

This study utilized secondary annual time-series data covering the period of the study. The data used is quantitative in nature, obtained from reliable sources, and publicly available. Specifically, data on financial development indicators such as financial infrastructure and financial deepening were obtained from the CBN Statistical Bulletin and the World Bank database.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.1. Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix measures how closely related two variables in the model are which can be used to check if multicollinearity exists or not. Multicollinearity in a model means there exists perfect or exact linear relationship in a model. If this exists, it violates the rule of OLS and our estimates become unreliable.

Table 1: Correlation Matrix Result

	ADNS	FDEVT	FIN	FDEVT_FIN	FI_FIN	FD_FIN	FINTEC_FIN	INSQ
ADNS	1.000000							
FDEVT	0.756170	1.000000						
FIN	0.644927	0.747007	1.000000					
FDEVT_FIN	0.751255	0.799552	0.727994	1.000000				
FI_FIN	0.700390	0.623237	0.669674	0.612925	1.000000			
FD_FIN	0.716629	0.622719	0.773218	0.606337	0.688839	1.000000		
FINTEC_FIN	0.734369	0.748511	0.609211	0.743979	0.743286	0.669857	1.000000	
INSQ	0.623097	0.643702	0.562059	0.647900	0.645328	0.628464	0.748587	1.000000

Source: Authors’ Compilation using Eviews 13.0

ADNS exhibited strong positive correlations with financial development (FDEVT), financial infrastructure (FIN), the interaction of FDEVT with FIN (FDEVT_FIN), FI’s interaction with FIN (FI_FIN), the moderation of FD with FIN (FD_FIN), the interaction of fintech with financial infrastructure (FINTEC_FIN), and INSQ indicating that greater access to financial services, increased digital finance usage, deepening, and strong institutions were all associated with enhanced and sustainable economic growth. From the findings, the coefficient values for all the

variables are below the threshold of 0.80. This clearly suggests that there is no multicollinearity in the model.

4.2. Augmented Dickey Fuller Stationarity Test

This subsection deals with the test of unit root. Since time series data usually exhibit unit root, ADF unit root test was employed to test for stationarity. This test is necessary so as not to have misleading results. The result is thus presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of the ADF and Structural Break Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF Statistic	ADF Critical Value @5%	Structural Break ADF Statistic	Structural Break Critical Value @5%	Order of Integration	Remark
ADNS	-7.7369	-2.9458	-9.0579	-4.4436	I(1)	Stationary
FDEVT	-3.1690	-2.9540	-6.1692	-4.4436	I(1)	Stationary
FI	-7.2928	-2.9458	-8.1906	-4.4436	I(1)	Stationary
FD	-4.3732	-2.9458	-7.1795	-4.4436	I(1)	Stationary
FINTEC	-6.9008	-2.9458	-8.5575	-4.4436	I(1)	Stationary
FIN	-4.8753	-2.9458	-5.4439	-4.4436	I(1)	Stationary
INSQ	-6.1024	-2.9458	-14.9315	-4.4436	I(1)	Stationary

Source: Authors' Compilation using Eviews 13.0

The ADF test reports that all variables are stationary at their first difference, i.e., I(1). That means all variables were stationary following the first difference. As all ADF statistics are more negative than their corresponding 5% critical values, the null hypothesis of a unit root (i.e., non-stationarity) is not accepted for all variables. This means that ADNS, FVET, FI, FD, FIN and INSQ all exhibit a difference-stationary process instead of a trend-stationary process. The fact that all the variables are I(1) suggests that they could be suitable for cointegration analysis to discover whether there exist any long-run equilibrium relationship between them. Since all the variables have the same order of integration, the Johansen cointegration test was employed to examine their long-run relationships.

4.3. Lag Length Selection

This section presents the appropriate lag length for this study before estimating the long and short run coefficients of the model.

Table 3: Summary of VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-82.27345	NA	2.40e-08	5.158483	5.513991	5.281204
1	-66.14696	301.3808*	4.15e-06*	7.182846*	9.942374*	8.257320*
2	-13.52389	57.40699	5.13e-06	7.403266	11.94488	8.785404

Source: Authors' Compilation using Eviews 13.0

The results from the VAR lag order selection criteria show that the optimal lag length of the models is 1, as it is evidenced by the lowest values of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Schwarz Criterion (SC) at this lag. This indicates that incorporating one lag reflects an appropriate balance between model complexity and goodness of fit. The results ensure that the models are well-specified and suitable for further analysis.

4.4. Johansen Cointegration Test

The next step after determining the order of integration of the variable is to apply the Johansen test in order to establish a long-run relationship among the variables. The results of the test are reported in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary Result of the Johansen Cointegration Test

Hypothesized No of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace statistic	Critical value @ 5%	Max-Eigen statistic	Critical value @ 5%
None *	0.866861	253.0974	159.5297	66.53999	52.36261
At most 1 *	0.785022	186.5574	125.6154	50.72831	46.23142
At most 2 *	0.705155	135.8290	95.75366	40.30313	40.07757
At most 3 *	0.663033	95.52592	69.81889	35.89638	33.87687
At most 4 *	0.508126	59.62954	47.85613	23.41456	27.58434
At most 5 *	0.443905	36.21498	29.79707	19.36491	21.13162
At most 6 *	0.388909	16.85007	15.49471	16.25279	14.26460
At most 7	0.017937	0.597281	3.841465	0.597281	3.841465

Source: Authors' Compilation using Eviews 13.0

The result shows considerable evidence of cointegration. The trace statistic verifies that at least seven cointegrating equations exist, while the max-eigen statistic also confirms the existence of five cointegrating equations. This shows a moderate degree of long-run relationship among the variables, which suggests they have a tendency towards equilibrium.

4.5. Vector Error Correction Mechanism

This method was conducted to determine the joint dynamic behaviour of a collection of variables without requiring strong restrictions to identify the underlying structural parameters. The results of the VECM are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Summary of VECM Result

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
COINTEQ1	-0.116809	0.095661	-4.221074	0.0000
D(ADNS(-1))	0.181076	0.223839	0.808957	0.4196
D(FDEVT(-1))	0.281186	0.901616	3.584677	0.0005
D(FIN(-1))	-0.079208	0.540445	-0.700582	0.4844
D(FDEVT_FIN(-1))	0.741643	0.187523	2.681956	0.0061
D(FI_FIN(-1))	-0.498078	0.655953	-1.825207	0.0695
D(FD_FIN(-1))	0.088211	0.184922	3.017785	0.0011
D(FINTEC_FIN(-1))	0.520838	0.280729	1.855305	0.0651
D(INSQ(-1))	0.018555	0.019600	2.946717	0.0050
C	-0.784138	0.488391	-3.951877	0.0004
R-squared	0.732612	F-statistic	9.770142	
Adjusted R-squared	0.655158			
S.E. of regression	0.215852			
Durbin-Watson stat	2.126553			

Source: Authors' Compilation using Eviews 13.0

The result shows the short-run dynamics and the rate of convergence to the long-run equilibrium. The error correction term (CointEq1) is -0.1168, which means that the deviations from the long-run equilibrium are being corrected at a rate of 12% per annum, implying a slow adjustment process. A 1% rise in the lagged value of ADNS causes a 0.18% rise in its current value, indicating a positive effect of previous economic growth on the current growth. Likewise, a 1% rise in the lagged value of FDEVT causes a 0.28% rise on sustainable economic growth indicating the positive contribution of financial development towards economic activities. The lagged value of financial infrastructure has a negative impact, as a 1% increase leads to a 0.079% decrease in sustainable economic growth. The interaction between financial development and financial infrastructure (FDEVT_FIN) has a positive and significant impact on sustainable economic growth, indicating that a 1% increase in FDEVT_FIN leads to a 0.74% rise in ADNS. The interaction of financial inclusion and financial infrastructure (FIN_FIN) also shows negative and insignificant impact on sustainable economic growth. It implies that on average, 1% increase in FIN_FIN reduces ADNS by about 0.50%. Similarly, when financial deepening interacts financial infrastructure (FD_FIN), it reveals a positive and significant impact of 0.088% on sustainable economic growth. The moderation of fintech with financial infrastructure (FINTEC_FIN) is found to have positive impact, with a 1% increase in its lagged value having a 0.52% contribution on sustainable economic growth, which is however statistically insignificant. The R^2 is 0.7326, implying that 73% variations in ADNS are explained by FDEVT, FIN, FDEVT_FIN, FI_FIN, FD_FIN, FINTEC_FIN, and INSQ, while only about 27% of the variables not explicitly captured in the model are explained by the error term. The percentage is quite high and this suggests that our models are good fit. With a Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.1266, the residual exhibits a slight indication of negative autocorrelation.

4.6. Post Estimation Tests

Table 6: Summary of Serial Correlation Test

Lag	LRE* stat	Df	Prob.	Rao F-stat	Df	Prob.
1	56.43178	64	0.7382	0.792418	(64, 52.6)	0.8136
2	47.05090	64	0.9447	0.621079	(64, 52.6)	0.9653

Source: Researchers' Compilation Using Eviews 13.0

The result reveals that the probability value for lag one and two are greater than the critical value at 5 percent level of significance. The study therefore accepts the null hypothesis which states that there is no serial correlation in the models.

Test for Heteroscedasticity

Table 7: Summary of Heteroscedasticity Test

Joint test:		
Chi-sq	Df	Prob.
458.4894	448	0.3557

Source: Researchers' Compilation Using Eviews 13.0

The purpose of the heteroscedasticity test is to determine whether or not each observation's error variance is constant or not. The probability value must be greater than the 0.05 level of significance

in order to support the null hypothesis that there is no heteroscedasticity in the residuals. Thus, based on Table 7’s findings, the probability value is equal to 0.3557 and this indicates that the significance level of the probability F statistic exceeds 0.05 percent. As a result, the study accepts the null hypothesis that the model does not exhibit heteroscedasticity in the residuals.

Table 8: Summary of Normality Test

Component	Jarque-Bera	Df	Prob.
1	0.334341	2	0.8461
2	0.424503	2	0.8088
3	9.630236	2	0.0081
4	0.170725	2	0.9182
5	1.015432	2	0.6019
6	1.349827	2	0.5092
7	5.791763	2	0.0553
8	1.595055	2	0.4504
Joint	20.31188	16	0.2065

*Approximate p-values do not account for coefficient Estimation

Source: Researcher’s Compilation Using Eviews 13.0

From the results, the joint probability value is 0.2065 and the observed p-values are higher than the 5% significance level (0.05). Hence, it strongly indicates that the test for normality of the null hypothesis cannot be rejected, meaning that the models' residuals are normally distributed, which is an essential assumption in econometric modeling.

These diagnostic test results show that the long-run relationship is robust and reliable despite the slow rate of adjustment to equilibrium.

4.7. Discussion of Findings

The findings indicate a slow adjustment to long-run equilibrium, showing that shocks persist in the economy. The previous growth affects the current growth positively since the past economic activities usually stimulate the current ones, and the financial development facilitates the growth by better credit allocation and resource mobilization. This is in line with the a priori expectations and the findings from the study of Alabi et al. (2024). Financial infrastructure alone limits the growth probably because of the inefficiencies and structural weaknesses it has, but when it is coupled with financial development and deepening, it raises their effectiveness and consequently the performance. Alabi et al. (2024) and Saramu et al. (2024) agree with this result, while also showing the concern of Noor et al. (2020) about the institutional bottlenecks. The positive implication of FINTEC_FIN comes from its ability to improve efficiency, access, and innovation, thus confirming Echu et al. (2024) on technology’s transformative impact. In contrast, financial inclusion with financial infrastructure shows a negative effect, as the provision of access without the institutional strength can lead to inefficiencies, thus backing up the findings of Tidjani and Madouri (2024) and Samuel et al. (2024). The insignificant but positive impact of financial deepening is because of the liquidity and credit expansion it offers, thus corroborating Salami and

Oluseyi (2013). Institutional quality (INSQ) shows a positive and significant but extremely small impact, a reflection of Nigeria's weak institutional framework under which the governance inefficiencies, corruption, and enforcement gaps collectively undermine the growth potentials that may accrue from institutions. This finding is partially consistent with the findings of Noor et al. (2020), who maintained that institutional and human capital indicators signify an inability to create growth when structural bottlenecks are present.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The finding that the interaction between financial development and financial infrastructure has a positive and significant impact on sustainable economic growth in Nigeria implies that financial infrastructure strengthens the effectiveness of financial development in promoting long-term growth. This means that improvements in financial inclusion, deepening, and technology yield greater developmental benefits when supported by efficient financial infrastructure such as robust payment systems, digital networks, regulatory institutions, and credit information systems. Therefore, financial infrastructure is the accelerator that amplifies the flow of financial services to the real economy, giving rise to investment, innovation, and productive activities that eventually lead to sustainable growth. Consequently, the finding underscores the need for building strong, tech-savvy, and inclusive financial infrastructure in the country so that the financial development not only leads to the economic growth that is both wide-reaching and environmentally friendly but also to the economic growth that is both wide-reaching and environmentally friendly in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the CBN in collaboration with the National Identity Management Commission (NIMC) and the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC) should establish a national financial infrastructure integration framework that digitally links credit registries, payment systems, land registries, and identity databases into a unified platform accessible to banks, fintech, and regulators. By doing this, financial infrastructure would not only support financial development but also directly translate into sustainable growth by reducing credit risk, cutting transaction costs, and expanding access to underserved populations. This integration solves the real-life problem of fragmented and inefficient financial systems in Nigeria, ensuring that financial development leads to inclusive and growth-enhancing outcomes.

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